

Quality Of Work Life And Organizational Performance: Workers' Feelings Of Job Security, Or Not, To The Organization's Productivity

Dr.G. SUGANTHI, Assistant professor and Head, Department of Business Administration, Thiru Kollanjiyapper Govt, Arts College, Virudhachallam, Cuddalore District.

Mrs.C.PUSHPALATHA, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Business Administration, Krishnasamy College of Science, Arts and Management for Women, Cuddalore.

Abstract

The main purpose of this research is to identify the significance of work environment towards the performance and also to study the effectiveness of the Quality of Work life in the organisation. In this research well-structured questionnaire was framed and data was collected using convenience sampling from 246 employees of the Chemical Industries in Cuddalore, and to study the significant association chi-square was used by the researcher. To find Quality of Work life of the employees of this Chemical Industries in Cuddalore can be improved by conducting some more training classes for the employees who are falling in the category of more than 3 to 4 years of experience which would boost their self-confidence and help them attain their level of satisfaction. Similarly, the organization can give some more security to the employees falling in the category of 41 and above so that they feel quite secure in the hand of organisation and they can give their high-level performance. This observation that empirical article on Quality of Work life – A Study's structured questionnaire can be applied as an Employee opinion Survey taken in once in 8 months on knowing the quality of work life. By doing this survey organisations can get to know the quality of work life of the employees and take necessary steps to improve the QWL among all the Employees. It also helps the employers to know that their employees who are working in their organisation are happily working leading to good Quality of Work life which will boost up their performance to come happily daily to their work place. In this survey, the employees how to balance between personal life and work life is to be measured and also measured how to improve their work performance.

Key Words: Human behaviour, Quality of work Life, Employee performance

INTRODUCTION:

The success of any organisation is highly dependent on how it attracts, recruits, motivates, and retains its work force. Today's organisations need to be more flexible so that they are equipped to develop their workforce and enjoy their commitment. Therefore, organisations are required to adopt a strategy to improve the employee's quality of work life to satisfy both the organisational objectives and employee needs.

Quality of work life is a process in an organisation which enables its members at all levels to participate actively and effectively in shaping organisational environment, methods and outcomes.

The current scenario is a knowledge worker and the society in which we are living has come, to be known as knowledge society. The intellectual pursuits have taken precedence over the physical efforts.

Some knowledge workers work for more than 70 hours a week. As a result of this, their personal hobbies and interests clash with their work. Life is a bundle that contains all the stands together and hence the need to balance work life with other related issues.

One must have found out differentiate between personal life and work life and both love and work in one's life to make it healthy. Gone are the days when the priority of employees used to be for physical and material needs. With the increasing shift of the economy towards knowledge economy, the meaning and the quality of work life has undergone a sudden change.

The main objective of this research is analysis of quality work life on employee's performance. quality of work life is fast becoming an imperative issue to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization in

every sector be it education, service sector, organization sector, tourism, manufacturing, etc. attrition, employees commitment, productivity etc. depend upon the dimensions of quality of work life i.e. job satisfaction, organizational commitment, reward and recognition, participative management, work life balance, proper grievances handling, welfare facilities, work environment, etc. an organization offers a better QWL then it grows the healthy working environment as well as pleased employee. high QWL can give a result in better organizational performance, effectiveness, innovativeness, etc. consequently, to contribute better life for all those peoples whom organizational members serve and with whom they deal and interact.

MEANING OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

Quality of work life refers to the favourableness or unfavourableness of a job environment for the people working in an organisation. The period of scientific management which focused solely on specialization and efficiency, has undergone a revolutionary change.

Work is an integral part of everyday life, as it is our livelihood or career or business. On an average we spent twelve hours daily life and it is the one third of our entire life. Research on quality of work life is considered to be more important at the individual and organization level.

Quality of work life is considered for both the employees and organization and it is involved with job satisfaction, productivity, job involvement, job enrichment etc. The success of any organisation is highly dependent on how it attracts recruits, motivates, and retains its workforce. Today's organisation needs to be more flexible so that they are equipped to develop their workforce and enjoy their commitment.

This study is made attempts to analyses the "Quality of work life among employees". In order to improve quality of work life, various copying techniques have been suggested to upgrade the employee's attitude towards their job and the working environment in the organisation. The traditional management gave inadequate attention to human values.

Major parts of quality of work life:

- Occupational healthcare
- Suitable working time
- Appropriate salary
- Good working environment
- Welfare facilities
- Grievance handling
- Good financial benefits

DEFINITION OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

The Quality of work as strategy of human resource management has assumed increasing interest and importance. Many other terms have to come to be used interchangeably with quality of work such as 'Humanisation of work' 'Quality of working life' 'Industrial democracy' and 'Participative work'.

According to **Nadler and Lawler** "Quality of working life is a way of thinking about people, work and organisations, its distinctive elements are,

- (i) A concern about the impact of work on people as well as on organisational effectiveness
- (ii) The idea of participation in organisational problem solving and decision making".

According to **Luthans**, "The overriding purpose of quality of work life is to change the climate at work so

that the human-technological interface leads to a better quality of work life”.

According to **Beinum**, “Quality of work life is based on general approach and an organization approach. The general approach includes all those factors affecting the physical, social, economic, psychological and cultural well – being of workers, while the organizational approach refers to the redesign and operation of organisation in accordance with the value of democratic society.”

According to **American society of training and development**, “Quality of work life is process of work organisations which enable its members at all levels to actively, participate in shaping the organisations environment, methods and outcomes. This value-based process is aimed towards

meeting the twin goals of enhanced effectiveness of organisations and improved quality of life at work for employees.

According to **Lloyd suttie**, “Quality of work life as the degree to which members of a particular organisation are able to satisfy important personal needs through their experiences in the organisation.”

OBJECTIVE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

- To know about the pay and stability of employment.
- To improve in various facilities to workers like salaries, benefits, and facilities.
- To study about alternative work schedules including work at home, flexible working hours, staggered hours, reduced work and part-time employment.
- To study about participative management, awarding the rewarding system.
- To study about increase in individual productive, accountability and commitment.
- To study better teamwork and communication.
- To study for improving the morale of employees.
- To study about reducing of organizational stress.

SCOPE OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE:

- ❖ To increase demands at work.
- ❖ To know about loss of long-term employee guarantee.
- ❖ The study helps us to know about key element of quality of work life.
- ❖ The need for enhanced work place skills.
- ❖ To know about greater competition for talent.
- ❖ To know about increased women in work force.
- ❖ To strengthen work place learning.
- ❖ To strengthen friends and family programs.
- ❖ To provide all employees with internet access.
- ❖ To increase investment in workplace learning.
- ❖ To improve the effectiveness of supervisors and team leaders.
- ❖ To improve better quality of life.
- ❖ To create global outlook and orientation among young professionals.

NEED OF THE STUDY:

The study is based that in the current scenario every organisation expects their employees to perform at their peak potential. Through monetary aspects play an important role in motivating employees, organization around the world have come to understand that there are many other aspects that contributes better employees' performance. It's aims to identify the various tangible and intangible aspects that contribute to the quality of the workplace. It is very important for an organization to create a very conducive working environment for employees. This research is needed to ensure that all employees are performing at their peak potential, free from stress and strain, and to ensure that all their needs are fully satisfied. It will be used as feedback from employees to know their current perspective of workplace and also to identify the areas of improvement for the organization.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Primary objectives:

- ❖ To find out the quality of work life of employees in Chemical Industries in Cuddalore.
- ❖ To study the attitude of employees towards various welfare measures provided in the unit under the study.
- ❖ To find out the employee's problems and offer suitable suggestions on the basis of the findings.
- ❖ To know whether quality of work life leads to improved productivity of the organization.
- ❖ To study whether quality of work life motivates the employees to learn further for present and future roles.

Secondary objectives:

- ❖ To identify measures to overcome these drawbacks.
- ❖ To know the real situation of the employees.
- ❖ To collect employee's opinion about this matter.
- ❖ To understand the relationship between quality of work life and employee's satisfaction.
- ❖ To know the level of employee's satisfaction.
- ❖ To study about benefits of individual employees from high quality of work-life in organizations.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

- ❖ The study helps in determining employee performance.
- ❖ The study shows the commitment of employees in Chemical Industries in Cuddalore.
- ❖ The study helps us improvement impact on shaping employee personality.
- ❖ To study shows the commitment to the organization and the society.
- ❖ To study help we to understand the major issues involved in quality of work life in Chemical Industries in Cuddalore.
- ❖ The study helps us to analyse quality of work life and its effect in organisation productivity
- ❖ To study help, know about the extend workers participation involved in quality of work life.
- ❖ The study helps to analyse the satisfaction level among the Chemical Industries (Cuddalore) employees towards quality of work life.

Negative point of the research

- ❖ The study is limited to the workers of in Chemical Industries in Cuddalore. and therefore, the findings of the study cannot be extended to other areas.
- ❖ Convenient sampling has been used in the study and it has its own limitations.
- ❖ Personal bias of the respondents might have crept in while answering a few questions in the structured interview schedule.
- ❖ Results of the study may not be generalized.
- ❖ The purpose from the sample not reveals the accurate facts.
- ❖ Lack of respondent's interest in answering the questions, and also might not have revealed true information.
- ❖ The study ignores important root causes of stress because they focus on the worker and not the environment.
- ❖ The time period for carrying out the research was short as a result of which many facts have been left unexplored. Lack of time and other resources as it was not possible to conduct surveys at large level.

Theoretical Foundation

Taylor (1979) more pragmatically identified the essential components of **Quality of working life** as; basic extrinsic job factors of wages, hours and working conditions, and the intrinsic job notions of the nature of the work itself. He suggested that relevant Quality of working life concepts may vary according to organization and employee group. **Mirvis and lawler (1984)** suggested that **Quality of working life** was associated with satisfaction with wages, hours and working conditions, describing the – basic elements of a good quality of work life as; safe work environment, equitable wages, equal employment opportunities and opportunities for advancement. **Baba and Jamal (1991)** listed what they described as typical indicators of **Quality of working life**, including: Job satisfaction, Job involvement, Work role ambiguity, Work role conflict, Work role overload, Job stress, Organizational commitment and Turn-over intentions.

Normal and Daud (2010) in their study – Investigating the relationship between Quality of work life and organizational commitment amongst employees in Malaysian firms say that the quality of work life of employee's job satisfaction and commitment. **Sayed and Sinha (1981)** examined the relationship between Quality of work life dimensions, job satisfaction and performance measures on the two groups of sample work in high quality of work life and low Quality of work life organizations. The result revealed that Quality of work life dimensions are related to job satisfaction in both types of organizations. A comparison between high and low quality of work life organization further

indicated systematic variation in the correlation pattern i.e., Organisation with low quality of work life tended to yield comparatively better relationship between Quality of work life dimensions and performance measures than the organization with high Quality of work life.

Singhal (1983), emphasized on the job quality of life where it is pointed out that quality of working life will be meaningful if the people working in organisation live a happy life in society. Economic, Family and Health related aspects to which employees are exposed as member of larger significant – society are significant factors that influence their quality of working life experience. He also made a point that Quality of work life is a time and situation bound concept that requires constant revisions and modifications as psycho-socio and organisational contents change over time. **Kontbluh (1984)** suggested that the contribution, of increased worker's participation in decision-making is appearing more often on labour management agenda as a strategy to increased employees Quality of work life. The reason for management interest includes need for (i) Increased profitability positive quality (ii) Improving quality of work life for

the new workers who are educated and have good work ethic, but are alienated and unmotivated under current management practices and (iii) meeting foreign compensation.

Chakraborty (1986) found out that there are many organizational situations which indicate hidden realities of Quality of work life. Researchers are required to examine the Quality of work life in light of new paradigm based on study of Indian psycho-philosophy offered from a strict problem- solving point of view and may have relevance to educate predicting managers. **Sinha (1986)** enumerated that modern workers demand jobs that satisfy their inner needs. In the light of content and process theories of motivation, it is postulated that the popular way of determining Quality of work life is to measure the attitude that constitutes job satisfaction. Moreover, it is also suggested that the prospects of better Quality of work life in India have to take sociological, psychological and related context into account. **Smith and Haims (2001)** have revealed that stress arises in the process of interaction between a person and a work environment that threatens the individuals physical and psychological. Physical illness and psychological disorders increase when pressure at work increases. Stress causes problems to the muscular system and circulation thus, increasing risk of myocardial infarction which is well documented psychosomatic studies.

Hackman and oldhams (1980) highlight the constructs of quality of work life in relation to the interaction between work environment and personal needs. The work environment that is able to fill employees ' personal needs is considered to provide a positive interaction effect, which will lead to an excellent quality of work life. They emphasized that the personal needs are satisfied when rewards from the organization, such as compensation, promotion, recognition and development meet their expectations. **Eberle (1990)** described that, the elements that are relevant to an individual's quality of

work life include the task, the physical work environment, social environment within the organization, administrative system and relationship between life on and off the job.

A Stephen, D Dhanapal (2011), “Quality of Work life and its impact on Organisational Excellence in Small Scale Industrial units: Employees perceptive” The present study attempts to analyse the employer’s perception on QWL is small scale Industrial units.

Harish K, Subashini K (2014), “Quality of Work Life in Indian Industries – A Case Study” The study include satisfaction of worker depends on adequate provident benefits and supportive financial benefit.

Sirgy et al. (2001) suggested that the key factors in quality of working life are

1. Need satisfaction based on job requirements,
2. Need satisfaction based on work environment,
3. Need satisfaction based on supervisory behaviour,
4. Need satisfaction based on ancillary programmes,
5. Organisational commitment.

Muftah (2011) mentioned that Quality of Work life (QWL) was one of the key areas of human resource management that is attracting attention and research focus. It was a philosophy that considers people as the most important resources in the organization and views them as an “asset” to the organization rather than as “cost”. Hence, if organization are concerned about developing

their human resources and gaining competitive advantage in market place, it seems necessary that they attend to one of their most precious assets, namely, their human resources by employing high quality working life experience in consonance their various needs eliciting favourable job-relate reposes in return (Chsdranshu Sinha,2012)

Research Methodology

The main objective of this study is to investigate and identify the significance of work environment

towards the performance and also to study the effectiveness of the Quality of Work life in the organization. In order to meet the stated objectives a structured questionnaire was framed and data was collected using convenience sampling from 246 employees of the Chemical Industries in Cuddalore, and to study the significant association chi-square was used by the researcher.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

- **Null Hypothesis (Ho):** There is no association between Age and Satisfaction level of Work Environment and job Security
- **Alternate Hypothesis (H1):** There is association between Age and Satisfaction level of Work Environment and job Security

Table No: 1 Showing the Chi- Square test for Association between Age and satisfaction on Work Environment and job Security (No. of respondents and the row percentages)

Age	Satisfaction level of Work Environment and job Security					Total	Chi-square Value	P-Value
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutral	Dissatisfied	Highly Dissatisfied			
< 20	28(70%)	10(25%)	12(30%)	14(35%)	16(40%)	80	40.94a	.000*
21-30	14(46.6%)	20(66.6%)	16(53.2%)	6(20%)	4(13.2%)	60		
31-40	38(88.36%)	26(60.4%)	8(18.6%)	10(23.2%)	4(9.2%)	86		
41-50	6(75%)	4(50%)	2(25%)	4(50%)	0(0%)	16		
> 50	1(50%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(50%)	0(0%)	4		
Total	88	60	38	36	24	246		

Table :1 Figure:1

The Table:1 analyses the relationship between Age and satisfaction of the employees Work Environment and job Security of the organisation. It is inferred that out of 246 respondents the respondents falling under the age group of < 20 and 21 – 30 and 31-40 are highly satisfied with 70%,66.6%, and 88.26% on the health and safety conditions of the organisation when compared to employees falling in the category of 41-50 and >50. The chi square value is 40.540. The calculated P value is less than 0.10%. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected at significant level of 10%, and we accept the alternative hypothesis and it says there is association between age and satisfaction of employees on Work Environment and job Security measures in the

organisation, it is also clear that people who are falling in the category of less than 40 years of age are either satisfied or highly satisfied with the Work Environment and job Security of the company than the employees falling under the category of 41 and above. Hence from the table it is inferred that there is association between Age and satisfaction of Work Environment and job Security in the organisation.

- **Null Hypothesis (Ho):** There is no association between training programmes and No. of years of experience.
- **Alternate Hypothesis (H1):** There is no association between training programmes and No. of years of experience.

Table No: 2 Showing the Chi- Square test for Association between training programmes and No of years of experience. (No. of respondents and the row percentages)

No.of Years of experie nce	Satisfaction level of training programmes					Total	Chi- square Value	P- Value
	Highly Satisfied	Satisfied	Neutr al	Dissatis fied	Highly Dissatisfi ed			
< 1yr	8(53.2%)	8(26.6)	8(53.3%)	2(13.6%)	0(0%)	30	81.88a	.000*
1-2 yrs	26(82%)	2(3.4%)	26(46.4%)	24(60.6%)	4(7%)	112		
2-3 yrs	4(16.6%)	8(33.2%)	28(116.6%)	6(25%)	2(8.2%)	48		
3 -4 yrs	12(66.6%)	8(44.4%)	6(46%)	6(33.2%)	4(22.2%)	36		
>4 yrs	8(80%)	8(80%)	0(0%)	4(40%)	0(0%)	20		
Total	78	30	76	52	10	246		

The Table: 2 analyses the relationship between years of experience and satisfaction of training programmes. It is inferred that out of 246 respondents 82% of the respondents with less than 2 years of experience feel that they are highly satisfied with training programmes conducted by organisation whereas 116.6% of the respondents falling in the category of 2-3 years' experience feels that the training programme

conducted in their organisation is neutral and 22.2% of the respondents falling in the category of 3-4 years feels that they are not satisfied with the training programmes conducted in their organisation. The chi square value is 81.11. Organization Reward System

- Design and Maintenance of Group and inter group relationship
- Managerial Practice and
- Internal and external strategies for change

Improved performance leads to improved quality of work life. Moreover, result revealed that quality of work life toward workers development like training of the employees, workers union, participation in decision making variables, management should come forward to meet worker's demand that they have positive impact on firm performance. The over all, performance of an organisation depends completely on the performance of its people, in spite of the organisation's size, purpose or other characteristics. Based on the discussion of the literature review, prior studies have established the relationship between QWL and performance. Quality of work life programs should be linked with such affective outcomes such as increased job satisfaction, improved employee performance to the extent that they develop employee participation in management, and involvement and responsibility of their work. Studies have also shown that there is an association between personality and job satisfaction and that there are many different personality factors which is correlated with job satisfaction. Again, broad research has proven that job fulfilment does not occur in standoffishness, as it is dependent on organizational variables such as structure, size, pay, working conditions, motivation and leadership style, which create the organizational culture & climate in the study of the Quality of Work Life mean to develop enhance and proper utilize human resource effectively, to improve Quality and Quantity of products, productivity, services and minimize the cost of production. Per unit of output and to satisfy basic needs, self-esteem of the workers psychological needs, their participation, and conceding in job, etc.,

Conclusion

QWL of the employees of this Chemical Industries can be improved by conducting some more training classes and provide good work environment for the employees who are falling in the category of more than 3 to 4 years of experience and >4 years of experience which would boost their self-confidence, job performance and help them attain their level of satisfaction. Similarly, the organization can give some more security (financial and non-financial, job security) to the employees falling in the category of 41 and above so that they feel quite secure in the hand of organization and they can give their supremacy performance. We must understand that half of our daily life is spent at work places and work life has become an integral part of our total life. Making work place happier has to be not only obligatory part of HR role but it is to be carried out by the HR functionaries with the same passion, spirit, enthusiasm, commitment and energy so management should make sure that all the employees working in their organization are happily working leading to good QWL which will boost up their performance to come happily daily to their work place.

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